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2 **ENERSI: Data-driven energy assessment services for** 3 **building refurbishment**

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13 **Abstract:** ENERSI is a platform which facilitates the development of innovative energy
14 assessment services based on the integration of data from multiple sources and domains (EPCs,
15 cadastre, socioeconomic data, statistical data, energy efficiency regulations, etc.). The integration of
16 these data is carried out using Semantic Web technologies. Specific services to meet the requirements
17 of different user profiles (e.g. building owners, energy certification agencies, and planning
18 departments) have been created to facilitate decision making in their specific realms. Two of these
19 services are described in this paper: one for building owners to assess the energy performance of their
20 property and take measures to improve it; and another for urban planners to identify the areas in
21 their municipality with the greatest potential for renovation.

22 **Keywords:** energy assessment services, energy performance certificates, building refurbishment,
23 semantic technologies
24

25 **1. Introduction**

26 In order to take decisions concerning the building retrofitting with the purpose of improving
27 energy performance, the different agents involved need to have information which is adapted to their
28 needs. Typically, building owners make decisions based on the costs that directly affect them, such
29 as how much they have to spend in the renovation and what the return on investment will be, rather
30 than in generic concerns about carbon emissions. Most probably, knowing that buildings are
31 responsible for 40% of energy consumption and 36% of carbon emissions in the EU would not
32 motivate an owner to undertake a renovation of their property [1]. Urban planners and politicians,
33 on the other hand, need to decide about the allocation of public funds to undertake large-scale, deep
34 renovation programmes. With this purpose, they need data about building characteristics, residents'
35 income, urban planning regulations, refurbishment programmes, among other. All of the agents that
36 intervene in the refurbishment of buildings need to have reliable information to take informed
37 decisions in their respective decision making realms. Often, these information is distributed in
38 different data sources, and available in multiple formats (web sites, data repositories, reports).
39 Therefore, it is difficult for these actors to put together all the information they need in a way that
40 they can easily understand it.

41 Several systems have been developed to collate accessible, reliable and understandable
42 information obtained from multiple sources. For example, E2KnowHow collects data from energy
43 experts – architects and consultants – to create a collective knowledge base which helps them to take
44 better informed decisions [2]. Another example is Construction21, which provides a social network
45 for the different agents in the construction sector to exchange information and experiences [3]. Other

46 systems gather energy-related data of buildings based on statistical data such as the EU Building
 47 Stock Observatory [4]. A last example is the INSMART project, which collects data from door-to-door
 48 surveys in a GIS-based energy information system [5].

49 A further step in this line of work is not only to gather and integrate data, but to provide ad-hoc
 50 services tailored to the needs to the agents that need energy-related data from different domains and
 51 sources to undertake refurbishment actions at different scales to improve the energy efficiency of
 52 buildings.

53 2. The ENERSI platform: integrating data, simulations tools, policies and methodologies

54 The aim of the ENERSI research project is to develop a platform that enables the creation of data-
 55 driven energy assessment services based on the integration and subsequent analysis of the integrated
 56 energy-related data. The platform developed in the project provides energy assessment services for
 57 three realms: architecture – analysing buildings’ performance to improve their energy efficiency –,
 58 energy distribution – improving the deployment of smart grids –, and service exploitation –
 59 integrating energy related data for citizens and companies to make use of them. In order to develop
 60 a new service, the data that users provide is enriched with the data already contained in the platform.
 61 This way, ad hoc energy services integrate the available data using the platform’s tools.

62 As an application case of the platform capabilities, two services have been developed to support
 63 decision-making in the field of building refurbishment: EnerVal, for building owners to assess the
 64 energy performance of their property and take measures to improve it; and EnerPlan for urban
 65 planners to identify the areas in their municipality with the highest renovation potential. The
 66 development of these services has been a process by which user requirements, refurbishment policies,
 67 energy-related data, and simulation tools become interrelated. This process cannot be systematized
 68 and it depends from the available data, information and tools with which the services to meet the
 69 requirements of the users are created. Therefore, a specific methodology needs to be developed ad
 70 hoc for each application case.

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Figure 1. Methodology to develop two data-driven energy assessment services for building refurbishment, EnerVal and EnerPlan.

74 The development of the two services have been carried out in four intertwined stages (Figure 1):
75 - Energy-related data sources have been integrated by means of a shared vocabulary (ontology).
76 This way, the multiple data sources have become unified in a semantic data model.
77 - Refurbishment policies and guidelines which suit the service requirements (i.e. to identify
78 refurbishment measures for the buildings selected by the users) have been identified.
79 -On-line simulation tools which are needed to propose renovation measures to the users, have
80 been selected and linked to the integrated data.
81 -User requirements have been validated through interviews and mock-ups in an iterative
82 process in interaction with the end-users.
83 The four stages have not been sequentially carried out, rather they have been activated
84 simultaneously. In this way, the intermediate outcomes generated in one stage have been used by
85 others. For example, as a consequence of the integration of a new data source, a new service
86 requirement was made by a user.

87 2.1. Integrating of energy-related data with Semantic Web technologies

88 The ENERSI platform collects data from multiple sources, formats, and domains including data
89 from energy performance certificates (EPC), geographical data, land registry, and census section. At
90 this point, 400,000 EPCs records facilitated by the Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN) have been
91 integrated with 8,000 records from the Geographical Information National Institute, data from
92 Spanish cadastral agency, 6,000 ITE reports (technical inspection of buildings) records from Catalan
93 Agency of Dwelling, and census sections data from National Institute of Statistics (Figure 2, [1]). In
94 ENERSI, we have applied Semantic Web technologies to integrate data from different sources (e.g.
95 relational databases, spreadsheets, text files, web pages) using standard languages such as RDF,
96 OWL, and SPARQL. The semantic data integration process encompasses three steps:

- 97 1) **Vocabulary agreement.** Development of an ontology that formalizes a shared
98 understanding of the meaning associated to the data. It includes concepts like “certificate”,
99 “performance”, and “energy consumption” among others. The ontology has been created
100 with the Click-On editor [6]
- 101 2) **Data modelling.** Generation of mappings between the ontology and the data sources. Each
102 data source has been mapped to the ontology using the R2RML standard mapping language.
103 The mappings have been created with Map-On tool [7]. Transformation of the data sources
104 into RDF. The mappings are executed to transform the data source into RDF according to
105 the ontology developed in Step 1. The mappings have been executed by Morph-RDB [8].
- 106 3) **Data linking and curation.** The data – in RDF format – is curated to eliminate errors such as
107 misspellings and invalid values. Moreover, the energy certificates have been enriched with
108 data obtained from the cadastre and census sections. Tailored scripts have been developed
109 to clean and enrich the data.

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112 2.2. Contextualising refurbishment policies and methodologies

113 With the aim of providing users with information about the possibilities of improving their
114 dwellings and buildings through rehabilitation, we have turned to existing policies. In Spain, the
115 reference policy is the long-term strategy for energy rehabilitation in the building sector (EREE, in
116 Spanish) [9], which has been adapted from the 4th article of the 2012/27 / EU Directive, released on
117 April 30, 2014. The data we have extracted from the EREE policy has been the following:

- 118 - *Clusters.* Categories used to cluster the Spanish residential building stock according to
119 building characteristics (year of construction, building use, number of floors, population
120 density) and deficiencies (lack of insulation, non-efficient systems). Each cluster describes
121 the constructive characteristics of the buildings.
- 122 - *Refurbishment scenarios.* For each of the clusters in which the Spanish residential stock has
123 been divided, the EREE suggests packages of refurbishment measures. Applying these

124 packages it is possible to achieve a decrease of 60% to 90% in heating energy consumption
125 and a 50% reduction of the energy supply for domestic hot water from solar sources.

126 In the implemented services, the criteria for the segmentation, identification of improvement
127 measures and definition of performance packages have been adopted from the EREE policy. From
128 the data obtained from the EPC's, the buildings have been grouped by year of construction, number
129 of floors and type of use (single-family or multi-family).

130 Thanks to this integration of data and refurbishment policies (Figure 2 [2]), it is possible to have
131 information on the energy savings and retrofitting costs of a group of buildings by applying the
132 measures of performance previously evaluated. This way, the users of the service can evaluate the
133 investments costs and the energy reduction resulting from the application of the renovation measures
134 to a selected group of buildings.

135 *2.3 Interfacing simulation tools*

136 The refurbishment scenarios for a building or a set of buildings in an urban area can be estimated
137 with a simulation tool, in our case, the simulator of rehabilitation measures developed by ICAEN
138 which is available on-line [10]. The refurbishment measures proposed by this tool are based on a
139 characterization study of the housing stock in Catalonia which have been assigned to a typology.

140 From the grouping of buildings and the identification of packages of improvement measures,
141 described in the previous section, the ICAEN simulator calculates the energy savings and the
142 estimation of rehabilitation costs. (Figure 2 [3]). In order to apply the simulation tool to a group of
143 buildings, the renovation measures implemented in the ICAEN simulator [11] have been matched to
144 the action packages proposed in the EREE. Thus, it has been possible to interrelate two methodologies
145 – the one used by the simulation tool, and the EREE policies- by means of the integrated data. The
146 EPCs provide this information but, if there is no EPC for the building, ENERSI searches for the
147 missing information in other data sources such as the cadastre, or the census unit. The outputs of the
148 tool are the energy savings, investment required to carry out the refurbishment, the return of
149 investment, and maintenance costs achieved by applying a package of measures. In this way, it has
150 been possible to automatically input in the simulation tools the required parameters (building use,
151 year of construction, and the climate zone) to make the simulation of a group of buildings.

152 *2.4 Capturing users' requirements*

153 One of the recurrent obstacles in the development of innovative energy services based on data
154 integration is the difficulty of end-users to envision the new possibilities that this integration offers
155 them. Knowing which new information could be obtained by integrating and analysing data from
156 multiple domains and sources, and for what and who it will be useful is by no means straightforward.
157 These questions cannot be answered only by the multidisciplinary team of experts designing and
158 implementing the services (in our case, architects, energy consultants and ontology engineers).
159 Therefore, the participation of end-users in the design of the services is fundamental. It is important
160 to discuss with them which data is available and what for, the policies and guidelines to be applied,
161 and the simulation tools to be interfaced (Figure 2 [4]). The requirements capture has been done
162 interviewing users and preparing mock-ups of the final applications. From the comments and
163 suggestions received, new questionnaires and mock-ups have been developed. In the first iterations,
164 static mock-ups were presented to the users and at the end of the requirements capture process
165 interactive ones were used. At this point of the process, users could visualize the best the
166 functionalities of the services.

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Figure 2. Process to develop the services: (1) Integrating energy-related data, (2) contextualizing refurbishment policies, (3) interfacing simulation tools, and (4) capturing user's requirements.

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3. Tailored energy assessment services

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The two services have been designed taking into account the knowledge and needs of the potential users. For instance, energy indicators cannot be shown in the same manner to a building owner than to an energy consultant. Similarly, in the service to experts the origin of the data and the operation of the methodologies are explained to the users. For both services, the purpose is to present the analysed information in a meaningful and understandable manner, using simple interfaces that guide the user through a sequence of few steps.

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3.1. EnerVal: Renew your property

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The service for building owners is named EnerVal. It enables owners to assess the energy performance of their building or dwelling, to compare it with similar buildings, to know which refurbishment measures would suit the building and their costs. At the start, the user searches the EPC of the property by introducing the address. Once the EPC is retrieved, the user gets information about the performance of the dwelling in relation to similar buildings (this means, buildings with the same construction year, climate zone, use, and built surface). Then, the impact of the refurbishing is assessed with a simulation tool which is automatically invoked using the characteristics of the building as inputs. Finally, the user receives information about government aid to finance the renovation costs.

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The user interface of EnerVal is shown in Figure 3. The users are guided through a wizard-like interface in a step-by-step fashion (1). The already integrated energy-related data is shown to the user (2). The source of the data is displayed so that users can understand where the data come from (3). The integrated data is shown in a way which suits the user's knowledge, in this case, someone who knows not much about building energy performance (4). Moreover, the refurbishment policies are used to contextualize the data (5). For example, the energy consumption of a building is referenced to maximum consumption specified by the refurbishment policy.

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Figure 3. EnerVal interface.

196 3.2. EnerPlan: Renew your city

197 The service for city planners is named EnerPlan. It helps users to know how the building stock
 198 in their municipality is performing – in terms of energy consumption and carbon emissions –, the
 199 renewal potential of the buildings, which buildings are more adequate to carry out refurbishment
 200 projects and their cost. At the start, the user finds an area of interest, typically a city, town or district.
 201 Once the area is located, the census sections are displayed in a map where the colour is related to the
 202 most common energy label in that area (Figure 4). EnerPlan summarizes the performance of the
 203 buildings in the area in bar charts. The user can focus on one type of buildings – such as those that
 204 have a D label, for example – to know the investment needed to carry out retrofitting measures and
 205 the energy savings achieved after the renovation of all the buildings in the area. Finally, the user
 206 obtains more detailed information on the retrofitting measures such as the return of investment and
 207 the maintenance costs, among others.

Figure 4. EnerPlan features.

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210 The main features of the interface are shown in Figure 4. First, a map shows the integrated energy-
 211 related data from multiple sources (EPCs, cadastre, census sections...) and aggregated data (1 and 2).
 212 The data can be displayed at different scales including province, county, and city (3). The buildings
 213 of a city are categorized in clusters based on the EREE policy (4). The actual performance of the
 214 buildings in the selected area is shown in dark colour, and the performance modified as a result of
 215 the application of the refurbishment measures is displayed in a lighter colour (5). These values are
 216 calculated using ICAEN's simulation tool. The economic indicators –investment and return of
 217 interest – are also provided by the tool (6). Finally, the users visualize the buildings to be retrofitted
 218 in a map and in a list which can be downloaded as a CSV file.

219 5. Conclusions

220 The assessment services developed in the ENERSI platform integrate energy-related data,
 221 simulations tools, policies and methodologies to meet the needs of different kind of users (building
 222 owners and city planners). In this paper, we have described the methodology we have followed to
 223 integrate energy-related data using Semantic Web technologies, to reuse existing refurbishment
 224 policies, to interface a simulation tool, to offer two types of end-users –building owners and planners-
 225 information which helps them to take decisions in their respective realms to improve building energy
 226 performance. At this point, the information they receive through these applications could not be
 227 acquired by other means.

228 The interlinking of the different components which intervene in the design of the new services
 229 – energy-related data integration, refurbishment policies, simulation tool and users' requirements –

230 can only be done based on the experience of the experts involved. In this process, it is necessary to
231 assess the components at hand, selecting from them the information that is required, making explicit
232 the criteria of the selection, so that the services as whole becomes trustworthy and intelligible for the
233 end-user.

234 One of the difficulties we faced in the development of the services was the alignment between
235 the users' requirements and the available data sources. It is difficult for users to envision innovative
236 services that come from the integration of data from other domains. This requires from users to think
237 differently as they do in their regular practice, opening up the possibility to include other factors in
238 their decision-making which they could not envision without the integration of data from multiple
239 domains. To help them to envision the new functionalities provided by the services, it is useful to
240 turn to interactive mock-ups.

241 The two services will be publicly available in the ENERSI web portal and in the websites of the
242 public institutions which have provided their energy data to the project. Following the feedback
243 received by the future users, the interfaces will be further developed and refined.

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